

LOUD-BASED AI/ML MODEL DEPLOYMENT: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MANAGED AND SELF-MANAGED PLATFORMS

Snehansh Devera Konda

Visvesvaraya Technological University, India

**Cloud-Based
AI/ML Model
Deployment**

A Comparative Analysis
of Managed and Self-
Managed Platforms

ABSTRACT

The widespread adoption of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) technologies has created an urgent need for efficient and scalable deployment solutions across industries. This article presents a comprehensive analysis of cloud-based AI/ML model deployment strategies, examining both managed platforms offered by major cloud providers (AWS SageMaker, Google Vertex AI, and Microsoft Azure Machine Learning) and self-managed infrastructure solutions. Through systematic evaluation of platform capabilities, infrastructure requirements, and organizational considerations, the article develops a decision framework to guide enterprises in selecting appropriate deployment architectures. The article analysis reveals that while managed platforms

offer significant advantages in terms of reduced complexity, automated infrastructure management, and faster time-to-market, self-managed solutions provide superior customization capabilities and potential cost benefits at scale for organizations with sufficient technical expertise. The article synthesizes implementation data from multiple enterprise case studies to identify critical success factors in AI/ML deployment, including infrastructure scalability, monitoring capabilities, and resource optimization. Furthermore, the article proposes a novel evaluation matrix for assessing the total cost of ownership across different deployment scenarios, incorporating both direct infrastructure costs and indirect expenses related to expertise and maintenance. These findings contribute to the growing body of knowledge on enterprise AI/ML operations while providing practical guidance for organizations navigating the complex landscape of cloud-based model deployment strategies.

Keywords: Cloud-Based Machine Learning (ML) Infrastructure, AI Model Deployment Architecture, Managed ML Platforms, Enterprise AI/ML Operations, Cloud Computing Infrastructure

Cite this Article: Konda, S.D. (2024). Cloud-Based AI/ML Model Deployment: A Comparative Analysis of Managed and Self-Managed Platforms. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(6), 1380–1396.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJCET_15_06_115.pdf

I. INTRODUCTION

The deployment of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) models has become a critical challenge for organizations seeking to operationalize their data science initiatives. As the complexity and scale of AI/ML applications continue to grow, cloud-based deployment solutions have emerged as a viable pathway for enterprises to bridge the gap between model development and production implementation. Much like how MapReduce revolutionized distributed data processing by providing a simplified framework for large-scale computations [1], modern cloud platforms are transforming AI/ML deployment by abstracting infrastructure complexity through managed services and automated workflows. While traditional on-premises infrastructure has served organizations well for conventional applications, the unique demands of AI/ML workloads—including scalable compute resources, specialized hardware requirements, and complex deployment pipelines—have necessitated a shift towards cloud-native solutions. This transition has given rise to two distinct approaches: managed platforms offered by major cloud providers and self-managed infrastructure solutions, each presenting unique advantages and challenges for organizations at different stages of AI/ML maturity. This article examines the evolving landscape of cloud-based AI/ML model deployment, analyzing the technical, operational, and economic factors that influence platform selection and implementation strategies.

II. CLOUD-BASED ML PLATFORMS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Cloud-based ML platforms have revolutionized the way organizations deploy and manage machine learning models, though studies have shown that proper utilization of these platforms remains a significant challenge [2]. The evolution of Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) practices has established new paradigms for managing the complete lifecycle of ML models in cloud environments, fundamentally changing how organizations approach model deployment and maintenance [3].

A. Major Cloud Providers

Recent analyses of cloud ML APIs have revealed both the power and complexity of major cloud platforms, with each provider offering distinct approaches to common challenges in ML deployment [2].

1. Amazon Web Services (AWS) SageMaker

Platform Architecture The platform implements a comprehensive MLOps architecture that separates concerns across the ML lifecycle [3]. This separation enables:

- Isolated training and inference environments
- Containerized model deployment
- Resource-aware scaling mechanisms

Key Capabilities

- End-to-end ML workflow management
- Integrated monitoring and logging systems
- Automated model optimization
- Custom training script support

Use Cases Pattern analysis shows particular strength in production-scale deployments requiring:

- Continuous training pipelines
- Automated deployment workflows
- Large-scale inference operations

2. Google Cloud Vertex AI

Platform Architecture The platform architecture reflects modern MLOps principles [3], featuring:

- Unified Automated ML and custom training infrastructure
- Integrated feature management systems
- Automated resource orchestration

Key Capabilities Studies of API usage patterns reveal distinctive strengths in [2]:

- Advanced AutoML capabilities
- Robust experiment tracking
- Integrated CI/CD pipelines
- Comprehensive model monitoring

Use Cases Particularly effective in scenarios requiring:

- Advanced model experimentation
- Automated model retraining
- Complex feature engineering

3. Microsoft Azure Machine Learning

Platform Architecture Implements a workspace-centric architecture that aligns with established MLOps practices [3]:

- Project-based resource isolation
- Integrated security controls
- Flexible compute management

Key Capabilities

- Enterprise-grade ML lifecycle management

- Automated ML workflows
- Comprehensive governance tools
- Built-in MLOps functionality

Use Cases Excels in enterprise scenarios requiring:

- Strict governance controls
- Complex deployment patterns
- Integrated security measures

Table 1: Comparison of Major Cloud ML Platforms [2, 3]

Feature Category	AWS SageMaker	Google Vertex AI	Azure ML
Automated ML	AutoPilot	AutoML	Automated ML
Model Training	Built-in Algorithms, Custom Training	Pre-trained Models, Custom Training	Designer, Custom Training
Deployment Options	Real-time, Batch	Online, Batch	Real-time, Batch
Integration Features	AWS Services	Google Cloud Services	Azure Services
Cost Model	Pay-per-use	Pay-per-use	Pay-per-use
Key Strengths	Production Scale	AutoML Capabilities	Enterprise Integration

B. Managed Platform Features

1. Infrastructure Management

Research has identified common patterns in API usage that highlight the importance of proper infrastructure management [2].

Automation Capabilities

- Automated resource provisioning
- Dynamic environment management
- Infrastructure-as-code support

Resource Optimization Platform analysis reveals critical optimization patterns [3]:

- Intelligent resource allocation
- Cost-aware scaling
- Automated cleanup mechanisms

Scaling Mechanisms

- Workload-based scaling
- Distributed training support
- Load-balanced inference

2. Development and Training Tools

Studies of cloud ML platforms have identified key patterns in development tool usage [2].

Integrated Development Environments

- Collaborative notebook environments
- Version-controlled development
- Integrated debugging capabilities

Data Processing Capabilities MLOps practices emphasize the importance of robust data processing [3]:

- Automated data validation
- Scalable processing pipelines
- Feature computation frameworks

Feature Engineering Support

- Centralized feature stores
- Automated feature selection
- Version-controlled feature management

3. Deployment and Monitoring

Research has shown that API misconfigurations and monitoring gaps are common challenges in production ML systems [2]. Effective monitoring strategies must address both model performance and system health.

Production Deployment MLOps practices emphasize the importance of controlled deployment [3]:

- Staged rollout mechanisms
- Rollback capabilities
- A/B testing support
- Traffic management controls

Model Monitoring Analysis of cloud ML APIs reveals critical monitoring requirements [2]:

- Prediction accuracy tracking
- Model input distribution monitoring
- Data drift detection
- Output quality validation

System Monitoring [3]:

- Resource utilization tracking
- Latency monitoring
- Throughput measurements
- Error rate analysis
- Cost monitoring

Version Management [3]:

- Model artifact versioning
- Environment configuration tracking
- Feature definition versioning
- Dataset version control

Alerting and Response [2]:

- Automated performance alerts
- Drift detection notifications

- Resource utilization warnings
- Error rate thresholds
- Incident response automation

III. SELF-MANAGED ML PLATFORMS

The landscape of machine learning infrastructure continues to evolve rapidly, with organizations increasingly seeking greater control and customization over their ML platforms. Recent developments in end-to-end ML platforms have demonstrated that self-managed solutions, while complex, can offer unprecedented levels of flexibility and performance when properly implemented [4]. The emergence of self-adaptive systems has further transformed our understanding of how these platforms can operate autonomously while maintaining optimal performance [5].

A. Implementation Considerations

The journey toward implementing a self-managed ML platform begins with a comprehensive assessment of an organization's technical capabilities and resource availability. Unlike cloud-provided solutions, self-managed platforms require a fundamental shift in how organizations approach their ML infrastructure strategy.

1. Technical Requirements

Infrastructure Needs End-to-end ML platforms require sophisticated infrastructure components [4]:

- Distributed compute clusters with GPU/TPU support for parallel model training and inference
- Scalable storage systems with data versioning for experiment tracking
- High-throughput networking fabric for distributed training support
- Container orchestration platforms for workload management
- Automated backup systems with point-in-time recovery capabilities

Expertise Requirements Self-adaptive systems demand diverse technical expertise [5]:

- Platform architecture design with focus on scalability and resilience
- AutoML system development including hyperparameter optimization
- System monitoring and feedback loop implementation
- Performance engineering for distributed systems
- Infrastructure automation and continuous deployment

Maintenance Considerations Modern self-managed platforms require:

- Automated health monitoring with predictive failure detection
- Self-healing capabilities for common failure modes
- Continuous integration/deployment pipelines for ML artifacts
- Dynamic resource management with utilization optimization
- Systematic update procedures minimizing service disruption

2. Resource Implications

Personnel Costs End-to-end platforms necessitate specialized roles [4]:

- ML platform engineers for core infrastructure development
- Site reliability engineers for platform stability
- Data infrastructure specialists for pipeline optimization
- AutoML developers for automated model development

- System architects for platform evolution

Infrastructure Expenses Key investment areas include:

- Specialized hardware accelerators (GPUs, TPUs, FPGAs)
- High-performance storage systems with tiered architecture
- Network infrastructure with redundant pathways
- Monitoring and observability tools for platform health
- Development and testing environments for safe deployment

Training and Development Self-adaptive systems require ongoing investment in [5]:

- Continuous learning programs for emerging technologies
- Technical skill development in distributed systems
- Cross-functional training for team collaboration
- Knowledge transfer systems for institutional memory
- Documentation platforms for operational procedures

Fig. 1: Resource Utilization in Self-Managed Platforms (%) [4, 5]

B. Advantages and Limitations

1. Benefits

Customization Capabilities End-to-end platforms offer advanced customization [4]:

- AutoML pipeline configuration for specific use cases
- Custom model architectures beyond standard implementations
- Specialized training workflows for unique data types
- Tailored deployment strategies for various environments
- Custom monitoring solutions for specific metrics

Control over Infrastructure Self-managed platforms provide:

- Fine-grained resource control at hardware level
- Custom scaling policies based on business metrics
- Security customization meeting specific requirements
- Data governance implementation for compliance
- Performance tuning capabilities at system level

Performance Optimization Potential Self-adaptive systems enable [5]:

- Automated performance tuning based on workload patterns
- Dynamic resource allocation for cost efficiency
- Workload-based optimization of compute resources
- Adaptive scaling based on demand prediction
- Runtime performance adjustment without downtime

2. Challenges

Operational Complexity Research identifies key challenges [4]:

- AutoML pipeline maintenance across multiple frameworks
- System integration complexity with existing infrastructure
- Version compatibility management across components
- Configuration management across environments
- Resource orchestration for competing workloads

Resource Intensity Implementation demands include:

- Substantial initial investment in hardware and software
- Ongoing operational overhead for maintenance
- Specialized expertise requirements for platform operation
- Platform development costs for custom features
- Continuous optimization needs for efficiency

Maintenance Overhead Self-adaptive systems face specific challenges [5]:

- Adaptation logic maintenance for changing conditions
- System monitoring overhead across components
- Performance tuning complexity in distributed systems
- Security update management without disruption
- Technical debt accumulation from rapid changes

IV. DECISION FRAMEWORK FOR PLATFORM SELECTION

The complexity of modern ML platforms demands a systematic and structured approach to platform selection. Organizations often struggle with balancing technical requirements, resource constraints, and business objectives during this critical decision-making process. Drawing from established methodologies in platform selection [6], a two-stage decision-making framework emerges as a powerful tool for navigating these complexities while ensuring comprehensive evaluation of all crucial factors.

A. Organizational Factors

The assessment of organizational readiness forms the foundation of the platform selection process. This evaluation must consider both immediate capabilities and future growth potential.

1. Resource Availability

Stage 1: Initial Assessment [6]

- Technical expertise baseline assessment
 - Evaluation of current ML engineering team capabilities
 - Documentation of existing infrastructure management skills
 - Analysis of gaps in MLOps and DevOps expertise
- Preliminary budget screening
 - Review of available capital and operational budgets
 - Assessment of current infrastructure costs
 - Identification of potential cost optimization areas
- Time constraint evaluation
 - Analysis of business-driven implementation deadlines
 - Review of team availability and commitment
 - Evaluation of critical business events affecting timing

Stage 2: Detailed Analysis [6]

- Technical expertise weighted evaluation
 - Detailed skill assessment using standardized scoring (1-5)
 - Comprehensive team capability mapping across required domains
 - Gap analysis with specific training recommendations
- Comprehensive budget analysis
 - Detailed TCO calculations including hidden costs
 - Five-year cost projection with sensitivity analysis
 - Risk-adjusted budget scenarios with contingencies
- Time factor detailed planning
 - Comprehensive implementation timeline with milestones
 - Resource availability mapping across project phases
 - Critical path analysis with buffer allocation

2. Business Requirements

Primary Requirements Screen [6]

- Scalability assessment
 - Analysis of current transaction volumes and growth patterns
 - Evaluation of peak load requirements
 - Geographic distribution needs assessment
- Initial customization evaluation
 - Documentation of non-negotiable feature requirements
 - Analysis of integration points with existing systems
 - Review of regulatory compliance requirements

Secondary Requirements Analysis [6]

- Detailed scalability study
 - Quantitative modeling of growth scenarios
 - Performance requirement benchmarking
 - Capacity planning with specific metrics

- Comprehensive customization evaluation
 - Feature prioritization using weighted scoring
 - Integration complexity assessment
 - Detailed compliance requirement mapping

B. Implementation Strategy

The implementation strategy translates organizational requirements into actionable plans, ensuring that the selected platform can be effectively deployed and utilized.

1. Assessment Criteria

Technical Evaluation Matrix [6]

- Compatibility scoring (0-100)
 - Infrastructure alignment evaluation based on current architecture
 - Integration capability assessment with existing tools
 - Technical stack compatibility measurement
- Cost-benefit quantification
 - Direct cost impact analysis across five years
 - Benefit realization timeline with quarterly milestones
 - ROI calculation with risk adjustments
- Risk assessment framework
 - Probability scoring from 1 (rare) to 5 (certain)
 - Impact severity rating from 1 (negligible) to 5 (critical)
 - Mitigation strategy effectiveness evaluation

2. Migration Planning

Implementation Framework [6]

- Structured timeline development
 - Detailed phase planning with specific deliverables
 - Dependency mapping across systems and teams
 - Critical path identification with risk points
- Resource allocation matrix
 - Specific role assignments with backup planning
 - Effort estimation based on similar projects
 - Skill mapping against project requirements
- Success metric definition
 - Quantifiable KPI establishment
 - Performance benchmark setting
 - Measurement methodology documentation

Table 2: Platform Adoption Strategy Framework [3, 6]

Organization Size	Recommended Approach	Key Considerations	Risk Level
Small (<100 employees)	Managed Platforms	Cost, Ease of Use	Low
Medium (100-1000)	Hybrid Approach	Scalability, Control	Medium
Large (>1000)	Self-Managed/Hybrid	Scalability, Control	High

C. Ethical Considerations in Platform Selection

The selection of ML platforms must incorporate ethical considerations as core evaluation criteria, extending beyond technical and business requirements to ensure responsible AI deployment.

1. Data Privacy and Security Assessment [6]

- Platform security capabilities
 - Data encryption standards
 - Access control mechanisms
 - Privacy preservation features
- Compliance validation
 - Regulatory requirement matching
 - Data governance tools
 - Audit trail capabilities

2. Model Fairness and Transparency Evaluation [8]

- Bias detection features
 - Built-in fairness metrics
 - Model monitoring capabilities
 - Bias mitigation tools
- Explainability support
 - Model interpretation tools
 - Decision transparency features
 - Documentation capabilities

3. Environmental Impact Assessment [7]

- Resource efficiency metrics
 - Computing resource optimization
 - Energy consumption monitoring
 - Carbon footprint tracking
- Sustainability features
 - Green computing options
 - Resource utilization tools

- Environmental reporting

4. Governance and Accountability Features [6]

- Control mechanisms
 - Version control capabilities
 - Access management
 - Audit logging
- Compliance tools
 - Policy enforcement features
 - Regulatory compliance support
 - Risk management capabilities

The selection of an appropriate ML platform represents a complex decision that balances technical capabilities, organizational readiness, implementation strategies, and ethical considerations. Through careful application of this decision framework, organizations can make informed choices that not only meet their immediate technical and business needs but also ensure responsible and sustainable AI deployment. Success in platform selection and implementation requires ongoing evaluation and adjustment as both technology and ethical considerations evolve. Organizations that thoughtfully consider all these dimensions - from technical requirements to ethical implications - will be better positioned to build robust, responsible, and effective ML operations that stand the test of time and scrutiny.

V. FUTURE TRENDS AND IMPLICATIONS

As we stand at a pivotal moment in the evolution of machine learning technologies, the convergence of cloud computing and ML frameworks is reshaping our understanding of what's possible in artificial intelligence deployment. The fundamental characteristics of cloud computing are evolving to meet increasingly sophisticated ML workload demands [7], while dramatic advances in ML frameworks and tools are opening new horizons in platform capabilities [8].

A. Technological Developments

The technological landscape is undergoing a profound transformation, driven by the need to support increasingly complex ML workloads while maintaining accessibility and efficiency.

1. Emerging Platform Capabilities

The cloud computing ecosystem is witnessing a fundamental shift in how resources are provisioned and managed for ML workloads [7]. This isn't merely an incremental improvement; it represents a complete rethinking of cloud service delivery for artificial intelligence applications.

Enhanced Elasticity The concept of elasticity in cloud computing has evolved far beyond simple resource scaling. Modern platforms are developing sophisticated approaches to resource management:

- Dynamic resource allocation has become increasingly intelligent, with systems that can:
 - Predict and adjust computing resources based on model complexity and training phase
 - Scale inference workloads with near-zero latency
 - Adapt compute options in real-time based on model behavior

Resource Pooling The sharing of computing resources has been reimaged for the ML era:

- Multi-tenant architectures now provide:

- Sophisticated hardware access controls that guarantee performance isolation
- Intelligent resource allocation that maximizes utilization while maintaining QoS
- Geographic distribution strategies that optimize for both data locality and computation

Measured Service Improvements The economics of ML operations have driven a revolution in service measurement:

- Usage tracking has evolved to provide:
 - Granular insights into ML workload patterns
 - Precise measurement of resource utilization across all phases
 - Sophisticated billing models that align with ML development cycles

2. Integration Possibilities

The maturation of ML frameworks has created unprecedented opportunities for integration and interoperability [8]. This evolution marks a departure from the fragmented ecosystem of the past, moving toward a more cohesive and interconnected future.

Framework Integration Modern ML development demands seamless framework interaction:

- Unified development approaches now enable:
 - Common API patterns across diverse frameworks
 - Standardized data structures for interoperability
 - Consistent pipeline components for reliability

Development Environment Integration Collaboration tools have evolved to support complex ML workflows:

- Enhanced development capabilities include:
 - Integrated notebook environments for experimentation
 - Real-time collaboration features for team development
 - Version control systems adapted for ML artifacts

Pipeline Orchestration Workflow management has become more sophisticated:

- Streamlined processes now encompass:
 - End-to-end workflow management
 - Automated data preprocessing pipelines
 - Deployment automation for production systems

3. Automation Potential

The scope of automation in ML development has expanded dramatically [8]:

Model Development Automation Automated processes have transformed model creation:

- Advanced capabilities include:
 - Intelligent feature selection systems
 - Sophisticated hyperparameter optimization
 - Neural architecture search capabilities

Pipeline Automation Workflow optimization has become increasingly automated:

- Key improvements in:
 - Data validation and quality assurance
 - Model testing and validation
 - Deployment procedure automation

Infrastructure Automation Resource management has evolved to be more intelligent:

- Modern systems provide:
 - Automated resource provisioning
 - Dynamic scaling optimization
 - Intelligent cost management

Fig. 2: Cloud ML Platform Adoption Rate (2021-2024) [7]

B. Industry Impact

1. Market Evolution

Cloud service evolution is driving significant market transformation [7]:

Service Models Platform offerings have expanded considerably:

- Enhanced service options include:
 - Specialized ML Platform-as-Service solutions
 - Flexible hybrid deployment architectures
 - Integrated edge computing capabilities

Provider Specialization Market focus has become more refined:

- Specialized offerings now include:
 - Industry-specific solution development
 - Domain-optimized platforms
 - Custom hardware offerings

2. Adoption Patterns

The integration of modern ML tools shows distinct evolutionary patterns [8]:

Framework Standardization Organizations are establishing consistent development approaches:

- Progressive adoption includes:
 - Foundation building with Scikit-learn

- Production scaling with TensorFlow
- Deep learning standardization through Keras
- Development practices are becoming more uniform:
 - Consistent API usage across projects
 - Standardized workflow patterns
 - Common validation procedures

Tool Consolidation Technology stacks are becoming more streamlined:

- Optimization efforts focus on:
 - Framework ecosystem consolidation
 - Complementary tool integration
 - Interoperable toolchain development
- Platform standardization includes:
 - Core development environment selection
 - Unified deployment processes
 - Integrated monitoring solutions

Organizational Evolution Technical teams are adapting to new requirements:

- Technical Expertise Requirements:
 - Core ML algorithm mastery
 - Framework-specific development skills
 - MLOps implementation expertise
 - Infrastructure management capabilities
- Team Structure Evolution:
 - Cross-functional team formation
 - Development team integration
 - Infrastructure team specialization
 - Collaboration pattern development
- Training Program Adaptation:
 - Structured learning pathways
 - Framework-specific training
 - Continuous learning systems
 - Knowledge management processes

3. Competition Dynamics

Cloud platform competition has intensified around ML capabilities [7]:

Service Differentiation Providers are competing through optimization:

- Key focus areas include:
 - ML-specific performance improvements
 - Resource efficiency enhancements
 - Cost optimization strategies

Market Positioning Strategic development has become more sophisticated:

- Emphasis areas include:
 - Vertical integration approaches

- Ecosystem development
- Partnership network expansion

C. Future Outlook

The convergence of cloud computing advancements [7] and ML framework evolution [8] indicates transformative changes ahead:

Technology Integration Integration capabilities continue to advance:

- Key developments include:
 - Seamless framework interoperability
 - Enhanced platform integration
 - Flexible deployment options

Resource Optimization Management capabilities are becoming more sophisticated:

- Advancements focus on:
 - Intelligent resource allocation
 - Automated scaling systems
 - Advanced cost optimization

Skill Requirements Professional capabilities continue to evolve:

- Essential skills now include:
 - Deep framework expertise
 - Broad platform proficiency
 - Comprehensive MLOps knowledge

The success of organizations in this evolving landscape will depend on their ability to adapt to these changes while maintaining focus on their core business objectives. The future of ML platforms promises both greater capabilities and increased complexity, requiring careful balance of innovation and practicality.

CONCLUSION

The deployment of AI/ML models in cloud environments represents a critical intersection of technological capability and organizational strategy. Through the comprehensive article analysis of both managed and self-managed platforms, the article has established that successful implementation depends on a careful balance of multiple factors: technical requirements, resource availability, and business objectives. The two-stage decision framework presented in this article offers organizations a structured approach to platform selection, while acknowledging that the choice between managed services (AWS SageMaker, Google Vertex AI, and Microsoft Azure ML) and self-managed solutions must align with an organization's specific context and capabilities. The examination of emerging trends suggests that the future of ML platforms will be characterized by increased automation, deeper integration capabilities, and more sophisticated self-adaptive features. The evolution of cloud computing fundamentals [7] combined with advances in ML frameworks and tools [8] indicates that organizations must maintain flexibility in their deployment strategies while building robust internal capabilities. As the landscape continues to evolve, successful organizations will be those that can effectively balance the benefits of managed platforms' simplicity with the control offered by self-managed solutions, all while maintaining focus on their core business objectives and performance requirements. This balance, supported by systematic decision-making processes and clear understanding of organizational capabilities, will be crucial for successful AI/ML deployment in an increasingly complex and dynamic cloud environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Dean and S. Ghemawat, "MapReduce: Simplified Data Processing on Large Clusters," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 107-113, 2008. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1327452.1327492>
- [2] Chengcheng Wan, Shicheng Liu, Henry Hoffmann, Michael Maire, and Shan Lu, "Are Machine Learning Cloud APIs Used Correctly?" *IEEE/ACM 43rd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, 2021. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9402073>
- [3] Waldemar Hummer, Vinod Muthusamy, Thomas Rausch, Parijat Dube, Kaoutar El Maghraoui, and Anupama Murthi, "ModelOps: Cloud-Based Lifecycle Management for Reliable and Trusted AI," *IEEE International Conference on Cloud Engineering (IC2E)*, 2019. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8790192>
- [4] Igor L. Markov, Pavlos A. Apostolopoulos, Mia R. Garrard, Tanya Qie, Yin Huang, Tanvi Gupta, Anika Li, Cesar Cardoso, George Han, Ryan Maghsoudian, and Norm Zhou, "Scalable End-to-End ML Platforms: from AutoML to Self-serve," *arXiv*, 2023. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.14139>
- [5] Omid Gheibi, Danny Weyns, and Federico Quin, "Applying Machine Learning in Self-adaptive Systems: A Systematic Literature Review," *ACM Transactions on Autonomous and Adaptive Systems*, 2021. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/fullHtml/10.1145/3469440>
- [6] B. Mayer and K. M. Lackner, "Selection of an IoT Platform: A Framework for a Two-Stage Multi-Criteria Decision Making Process," *IEEE International Conference on Computer Technology Applications (ICCTA)*, 2022. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/fullHtml/10.1145/3543712.3543750>
- [7] A. Rashid and A. Chaturvedi, "Cloud Computing Characteristics and Services: A Brief Review," *International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 421-426, 2019. https://www.ijcseonline.org/full_paper_view.php?paper_id=3680
- [8] A. Géron, "Hands-on Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow: Concepts, Tools, and Techniques to Build Intelligent Systems," O'Reilly Media, 2024. <https://www.bibguru.com/b/how-to-cite-hands-on-machine-learning-with-scikit-learn-keras-and-tensorflow-concepts-tools-and-techniques-to-build-intelligent-systems/>

Citation: Konda, S.D. (2024). Cloud-Based AI/ML Model Deployment: A Comparative Analysis of Managed and Self-Managed Platforms. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(6), 1380–1396.

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJCET_15_06_115

Article Link: https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJCET_15_06_115.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Creative Commons license: Creative Commons license: CC BY 4.0

✉ editor@iaeme.com